

THE CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, JOB SATISFACTION AND PRODUCTIVITY OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya¹ⁱ, Rosaline Oluremi Opeke²

¹PhD, Chief Librarian/Lecturer, Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary,
Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria

²PhD, Professor, Information Resources Management, Babcock University,
Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

Abstract:

This study investigated relationship between emotional intelligence, job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in Nigerian public universities. A correlational survey research design was adopted. The study population consisted of 1,254 librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria, from which 923 were selected using simple random sampling. The research instrument used was a self-developed questionnaire. Its validation was subjected to the scrutiny of experts in the areas of the variables studied; it gave a reliability coefficient of 0.91 for Emotional Intelligence; 0.78 for Job Satisfaction; and 0.94 for Productivity. A response rate of 67.2% was achieved. Data were analysed using descriptive (percentage, mean, average mean and standard deviation) and inferential (Pearson Product Moment Correlation) statistics. The study revealed a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction ($r = 0.034$, $P < 0.05$), between emotional intelligence and productivity ($r = 0.032$, $P < 0.05$) of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria. The study concluded that contrary to general belief, job satisfaction and productivity levels of librarians in university libraries were high. It is recommended that university library management should continue to promote values that would boost emotional intelligence and increase job satisfaction and productivity of its workforce.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, emotional intelligence competencies, librarians, job satisfaction, productivity, public university libraries

ⁱ Corresponding author: Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, PhD e-mail yjapheth@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

Emotional Intelligence of employees plays a crucial role in enhancing the job satisfaction and productivity of workers in any organization. According to Somvir and Kaushik (2012), job refers to occupational act that is carried out by an individual or group of individuals in return for a reward, while satisfaction refers to the way one feels about events, rewards, people, relation and amount of mental gladness on the job. Job could also be defined as work for which one receives regular payment or appreciation. Hence, job satisfaction can be defined as an emotional response to a job situation which cannot be seen, but only be inferred. It is simply regarded as how people feel about their job and different aspects of it. It means a positive attitude that an individual has from what he does to earn a living. Similarly, Gamlath and Kaluarachchi (2014, p. 54) see job satisfaction as the rate at which “employees like or dislike their work and the extent to which their expectations concerning work have been fulfilled”. Job satisfaction is generally acknowledged as a necessary ingredient for personal fulfilment in carrying out one’s duties. It could be noted that employees that enjoy job satisfaction will display high degree of commitment to their tasks in the organization; there is need for strong and effective job satisfaction indicators such as employee recognition, career advancement opportunity, conducive working environment, reasonable salaries and wages among others.

Thus, job satisfaction enhances productivity of workers in any organization especially in the public university libraries as a satisfied worker is a happy and productive worker. Contrarily, Ademodi and Akintomide (2015) posited that a dissatisfied worker will either resign his or her appointment from the organization or constitute nuisance to the organization and this will encourage inefficiency and low productivity or commitment. It is therefore expedient for every “manager to take initiative in finding out those factors that improve job satisfaction of the subordinates” (Vijayabanu & Swaminathan, 2016, p. 1638) in order to boost productivity and enhances retention of the experienced workforce in the organization.

Emotional intelligence is a psychological term that enables an individual to know and manage his or her feelings and emotions and use this information to guide his/her thinking and action while relating with other people in the organization and in the larger society. EI skills are essential in determining not only employee job commitment and job satisfaction, but also the level of employee productivity in the organization (Masrek et al, 2012). It is a known fact that librarians on daily basis relate with different categories of library users that have diverse feelings and emotions. Thus, it is expected of every librarian to possess some measurements of emotional intelligence

competencies (EICs) that would enable him or her to adequately meet the information needs of library users. These EICs could be acquired through constant training and continuous career development on the part of librarians in order to make their services more relevant in this information age.

In Nigeria, there are eighty one (81) public universities (National University Commission, 2015). The list comprises of forty one (41) Federal universities and forty (40) State owned universities. These universities are spread amongst the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Research has shown that the level of job satisfaction and productivity of library personnel is low (Babalola & Nwalo, 2013) although their research productivity is relatively high (Okonedo, Popoola, Emmanuel & Bamigboye, 2015). While many of these studies have been directed towards library use, library collections and library services, few if any have been carried out from the perspective of personal welfare of employees. In other words, studies have not been directed at investigating the relationships between welfare and personal issues such as emotional intelligence on one side and job satisfaction and productivity on the other side. The aim of this research is to find out the relationships among these variables; specifically, the extent to which emotional intelligence influences the job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in university libraries in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The general objective of this research work is to investigate how emotional intelligence correlates the job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in Nigerian public university libraries. The specific objectives are to:

1. determine the degree of job satisfaction of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria;
2. find out the level of productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria;
3. assess the level of emotional intelligence of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria;
4. investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria; and

5. evaluate the relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following are the list of research questions slated for this research work:

1. What is the degree of job satisfaction of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?
2. What is the level of productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?
3. What is the level of emotional intelligence of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria; and

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to librarians in the public (that is, federal and state) universities in Nigeria. This means that private universities and other third level institutions were excluded. Respondents were librarians in the federal and state universities that are spread across the six geopolitical regions in Nigeria. Para-professional staffers as well as other personnel of the libraries were thus excluded because the researchers believed that librarians are the custodians of information resources that are kept in the university library; they are the policy makers as well as managers of other library personnel.

Besides, they were concerned with those motivating factors that influence the job satisfaction and productivity of librarians while those factors that motivate other library personnel and users were excluded. The study examined all the four emotional intelligence (EI) components as well as twenty six (26) EI competencies that relate to job satisfaction and productivity of librarians while those EI competencies of other library personnel were excluded.

Review of Literature

Employee Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence

Results of different research studies conducted by some scholars from different subject field of knowledge shown that there is significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and emotional intelligence; and people (employees) with less workplace stress enjoy a higher level of job satisfaction (Thomas & Tram, 2006; Ghoniem, Elkhoully, Mohsen & Ibrahim, 2011; Cekmecelioglu et al, 2012; Mousavi et al, 2012; Emdady & Bagheri, 2013; Shooshtarian et al, 2013; Masrek , Osman, Khamis & Paiman, 2014; Khugshal, Rawat & Chaubey, 2014; Orhan & Dincer, 2014; Quang, Khuong & Le, 2015). Various researchers have come to the conclusion that people with higher emotional intelligence are at a favourable level of life satisfaction, while job satisfaction is a small portion of the larger concept of life satisfaction. Rebello (2011) from the results of his study revealed that there is connectivity between emotional intelligence and employee productivity. He posits that a teacher/ lecturer with better emotional intelligence can perform better in-terms of class delivery, leading the team & building trust among colleagues and the surrounding network.

This issue was confirmed by the research of Sy, Tram, Linda A. O'Hara (2006) examined the relationship between managers' and employees' emotional intelligence with the job satisfaction and job performance they have. As a result of this study, it has been understood that there is a strong relationship among these variables, and this positive relation has a high influence on the level of employees' job satisfaction which also increases the job performance and productivity. In addition to this, two other studies also proved the positive impact of emotional intelligence on job satisfaction and job performance (Kafetsiosa & Zampetakis, 2008). According to regression analysis used in these studies, the use and regulation of emotions have been more effective in terms of job satisfaction level rather than all other dimensions of EI.

The same result was also acquired by Guleryüz, Guney, Aydin and Asan (2008, p.1632); Orhan and Dincer (2014, p. 618). Also, it can be established from the studies conducted by Ogungbeni et al (2013) and Mousavi et al (2012) that there is a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence of librarians as well as primary education teachers and their job satisfaction. It is clear from the findings of these researchers that emotional intelligence affects job satisfaction of employees in any organization. This implies that there is direct relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of librarians in the university library. Martinez (1997) referred to emotional intelligence as a set of non-cognitive skills, abilities, and capacities that make the individual resistant to external demands and undue pressures. Moreover,

the most important factor in achieving goals of any organization is manpower; and doubtlessly the success and progress of any organization depends on its human resources (Mousavi et al, 2012).

University libraries are service delivery institutions in which most of its human resources are hardworking, committed individuals and painstaking at providing educational resources that readily meet the information needs of its users within and outside the university community. Hence, the feelings and personal needs of those librarians and other personnel working in such organization needed to be adequately taken care of by their employers so that they can render selfless service to their clients as demanded of them by their profession. It could be reiterated here that librarians are not wood or stone; they are human being that have moods, feelings and personal needs which should be adequately catered for by their employers if they are to be maximally productive in their choosing profession as demanded from them by their employers.

Emotional intelligence as noted by Cekmecelioglu et al(2012, p.364) is a “sub set of social intelligence, involves the ability to monitor one’s own and others’ feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and use this information to guide one’s thinking and actions”. This definition of emotional intelligence addresses the four-dimensional emotional intelligence construct consisting of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and social management (Kelly & Barsade, 2001; Caruso, Mayer & Salovey, 2002; Salovey & Pizarro, 2003; Rubin, Munz & Bommer, 2005; Cote & Miners, 2006).

Along with these widely accepted four-dimensional construct, there are other typologies (classifications) and categorizations of emotional intelligence. For example, Reus and Liu (2004) proposed two main components of emotional intelligence: emotional recognition and emotional regulation. Emotional recognition refers to a person’s ability to perceive emotions and understand their potential causes and effects (Reus & Liu, 2004). On the other hand Emotional regulation is the ability of individuals to manage their own and others emotional expressions.

These two classifications or sub-processes of emotional intelligence appear to be narrowly defined versions of previous emotional intelligence constructs. Goleman (1995) classified it into internal and external elements. The internal elements include self-awareness, self-concept, independence, self-actualization, and decisiveness while the external factors include interpersonal relationships, empathy, and responsibility. These factors are related to the productivity of employees in any organization, especially in the university library that relate with several clientele on a daily basis.

Moreover, emotional intelligence involves the capacity of the individual for accepting the realities of life, the ability to solve emotional problems, and the ability to cope with stress, impulses and remain committed to the organization in achieving its

goals and objectives (Jorfi, Jorfi & Moghadam, 2010; Mousavi et al, 2012; Johar & Shar, 2014).

In most organizations, people are freely interacting with others regardless of what their position may be in order to have a high level of efficiency and job performance. Thus, to achieve one's stated goals in life, there is need to have "effective relationship with others who are adequately equipped with technical abilities along with certain characteristics which we refer to as emotional intelligence competencies. It can be noted here that these abilities make the individual self-aware, composed, respectable, observant, supportive, participative, visionary, calm and receptive in confrontation with others or situations. In Goleman's word, "emotional intelligence consists of self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills" (Mousavi et al, 2012, p. 782).

In contrast, Millet (2007) arrived at the conclusion that the relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction is not significant in police officers. There exists a weak negative relationship between stress management component of emotional intelligence and a weak positive relationship between adjustment and general mood components of emotional intelligence and job satisfaction; yet, these relationships are not significant. Quang et al (2015) concluded in their study that leaders in any organization of labour should manipulate their emotions in order to promote the level of workforce engagement at workplace. Furthermore, Tal Millet mentions that emotional intelligence and job control can account for 26% of job satisfaction variance.

Nevertheless, Kafetsios and Zampetakis (2007) on their part concluded that emotional intelligence is an important predictor of job satisfaction and this enhances productivity of workers in the organization. Moreover, only the component of recognizing other's emotions had a significant relationship with job satisfaction. It presented some competencies that enable manager to effectively relate with other people within the organization in achieving its stated goals. Also, Lopes et al (2006) in their study revealed that emotionally intelligent individuals received greater merit increases and held higher company rank than their counterparts. They further assert that those workers received better peer and/or supervisor ratings of interpersonal facilitation and stress tolerance than their counterparts with low emotional intelligent skills.

Therefore, librarians in the university library should possess high emotional intelligent skills that would enable them enjoy their working relations with their counterparts and library patrons who they relate with on daily basis. These would equally increase the level of their productivity in the university library.

Employee Productivity and Effects of Emotional Intelligence Competencies on Librarians

Many studies had been conducted by some scholars to establish the relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of employees in the organization; few of these studies are here presented in this study. Sahdat, Sajjad, Farooq and Rehman (2011); in their study concluded that high emotional intelligence employees between managers can manage the levels of work life; and that there is a need to develop emotional Intelligence competencies in persons to improve administrative performance and practices. Kahtani (2013) in his study affirmed that Employee Emotional Intelligence enhances Employee Performance in the Higher Education Institutions in Saudi Arabia; he concluded the study by proposing a theoretical framework highlighting the link between emotional intelligence (EI) and performance. Orluwene and Wachikwu (2014) revealed significant value for all the four dimensions of emotional intelligence, self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management implies that both interpersonal and intrapersonal competence of emotional intelligence are key factors to being resilient in the face of some stressful work like that of the teachers. And that emotion is contagious.

In a related development, from the study conducted by Zaki, Hasan and Manzoor (2012) on the influence of emotional intelligence on employees' leadership skills – strategic approach towards organizational stability; it was concluded that the positive involvement of leadership effectiveness with properly utilized components of emotional intelligence (self-regulation, empathy, recognition, motivation and communal skills) will enhance the organizational productivity and performance. Still on emotional intelligence components, EBSCO Competency Center (2013) further explained EI competencies like Self-regulation: When faced with problems and crises, managers and executives who self-regulate react thoughtfully and focus on causes and possible solutions. Motivation: Managers (librarians) with motivation excel, and they inspire their subordinates to also excel. Empathy: Empathy enables team leaders (librarians) to assess team members' (subordinates') agendas and feelings, accommodate cultural differences when working with clients and colleagues, and more effectively motivate them. Social skill: Socially skilled managers and executives can rally employees to achieve business goals and transform vision into reality.

Similarly, Goleman (2005) asserted in his book that mixed model of Emotional Intelligence operates under the assumption that it can be used to enhance the performance and effectiveness of individuals. He posited that emotional competencies are leaned capabilities that must be worked on and developed to achieve outstanding

performance. Again, that, individuals are born with a general Emotional Intelligence that determines their potentials for learning, achieving and performing (Goleman, 1998). Hence, the researchers concur with these authors' submissions; as a librarian who possesses the emotional skills like empathy, recognition of other employees feelings and develop strategies in motivating workforce that are under his leadership will achieve higher level of productivity than his counterparts that possess less degree of emotional intelligence leadership skills. Swanson and Zobisch (2014) posited that EI has proven to be an effective skill leading to an individual's overall success in the workplace.

Besides, Salovey and Mayer (1990) primarily characterized most popular ability models of emotional intelligence in relationship to the manager's performance in the organization as a set of four exact cognitive natural forces that enhance his capability to recognize, cause with and utilize strong sentiments effectively. Specifically, he must possess the proficiencies to: perceive emotion; integrate emotion to facilitate thought; understand emotions; and manage emotions of his subordinates and clients so as to enhance his productivity in the organization. In support of Salovey's submission, it can be noted that emotional intelligence is a basic ability for learning and a key feature for efficient leadership (Yong, 2013; Javidparvar, Hosseini&Berjisian, 2013). Managing emotions by skills of controlling motions has relationship with managing through emotions. Managing emotions practically is related to how individuals behave with each other especially in the workplace or in the entire human society; therefore, in educational organizations such as the university library, librarian's roles in processing and disseminating relevant information to the information seekers are considered important. This skill helps individuals in self-regulation, being responsible to others, respecting others' views and articulating feelings. Managing emotions is a skill which approves the importance of leadership status in determining educational tasks, performing educational process sufficiently and self-esteem (Javidparvar et al, 2013).

However, from the findings of a study carried out by an unknown author it was discovered that emotional intelligence of employees had an impact on their level of job performance. This has implications for management, suggesting that organizations could be profitable by identifying the level of emotional intelligence of employees and apply interventions that are focused on the developing emotional intelligence among the employees in the organization (Anonymous author, n.d). The author further stressed that EI is associated with better performance in the following areas: participative management; pulling people at ease; balance between personal life and work; straight forwardness and composure; decisiveness; doing whatever it takes to succeed; adaptability and confronting problem of the employees in the organization. He

noted that most of the organizations employ employees that are emotionally intelligent, so that they can face the workplace problems easily and can be more productive for the organization.

The researchers concur with these authors' submissions as they further reinforced his earlier position that there is strong link between EI and productivity of workers in any organization especially in the university library; librarians should be emotionally intelligent due to the nature of their duties as managers of human (users & library staff) and custodians of educational resources stocked in the university library. Therefore, they should be in total control of their moods and feelings so that they can manage the emotions of other people under their leadership in the university library. Also, every librarian should be emotionally intelligent so that they can be skilful in managing the occupational stress that abounds in the university library due to the nature of his work. This helps in improving the general health condition of the library staff and eventually enhances their overall productivity in the entire university community which the university library intends to serve.

Generally, the Emotional Intelligence (EI) is made up of the following five main components: Self-Awareness, Social Awareness, Self-Management and Relationship Management. Interestingly, these EI components are inter-connected and they are further divided into some minor sets known as emotional intelligence competencies (EICs). Emotional intelligence competences (EICs) are what result and enhance our personal, relational and professional performance, and what ultimately help us attain an overall increase in our quality of life (Ziv, 2014). In a related development, Goleman (2002) defined Emotional Competence as a learned ability grounded in Emotional Intelligence. Goleman (2002) reviewed his earlier work of 1998 and later collapsed most of the EICs; nonetheless this study adapts Goleman (1998) framework as well as that of Ziv (2014) model; thus, the five main EI components with the twenty six EICs used for this study are succinctly presented in table 1 below:

Table 1: A Framework of Emotional Intelligence Components showing Twenty Six Competencies used for this study

	Self-personal competence	Other social competence
Recognition	Self-Awareness - Emotional self-awareness - Accurate self-assessment/evaluation - Self-confidence/esteem	Social Awareness - Empathy - Achievement/service orientation - Organizational awareness - Organizational commitment - Leadership
Regulation	Self-Management - Self-control - Trustworthiness - Conscientiousness - Adaptability - Achievement drive - Optimism/ <i>Positivism</i> - Initiative - Innovation - Growth Orientation	Relationship Management - Developing others - Influence - Communication - Conflict management - Positive impact on others - Change catalyst - Building bonds - Teamwork - Collaboration & Cooperation

Sources: Goleman (2002) and Ziv (2014).

Methodology

Research Design

The correlational research design was used for this study. According to Cheng (2016), correlational research design could be used to describe the relationship between two or more variables, as well as how strongly these variables relates to one another. In other words, it aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables and the strength of this relationship.

In the same vein, Kowalczyk (2015) posits that the whole purpose of using correlations in research is to figure out which variables are connected. The researchers concur with these authors' assertions. Thus, correlational research design was adopted for this study in order to establish the relationships between the variables.

Population

The population for this study consisted of 1,254 librarians from the 81 public universities (Federal & State) in Nigeria. The list comprised of 41 Federal universities and 40 State owned universities.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size for this study is 923 librarians. Random sampling technique was adopted for this study. The sampling was done by first stratifying the country (Nigeria) along the existing six geopolitical zones (strata); these include: North-Central, North-East, North-West, South-East, South-South and South-West. Each zone (stratum) is made up of six States except North-West and South East that are made up of seven and five States respectively.

Consequently, the researchers surveyed all the librarians in all the public university libraries established in the four selected geopolitical zones and states. They randomly selected 60% sample size from the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria which give approximately four zones; these included: North-Central, North-West, South-East and South-West. The number of librarians in the fifty four (54) selected public university libraries considered for this study was calculated at 923.

Research Instrument

The researchers employed the questionnaire in collecting data for this study. The questionnaire for this study was designed by them. The research instrument was divided into four sections: A, B, C and D. Items in the instrument were gathered from the literature reviewed for the study.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The research instrument was subjected to the scrutiny of some university librarians especially those with PhD degree in the field of librarianship and other experts in the areas of the variables studied; these were approached for their useful advice and input in order to validate the research instrument used for the study. Both face and content validity were employed in order to standardise the instrument and to make it more adequate for the study. Based on their useful feedback, the research instrument was modified where necessary.

A pilot study was conducted. The researchers through friends and research assistants administered 56 questionnaires and retrieved 38 copies (67.9%); among professional librarians of three public university libraries that were not part of the sample for the main study. These were subjected to Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis and with alpha reliability coefficient results as follows: Emotional Intelligence of Librarians $\alpha = 0.91$; Job Satisfaction of Librarians $\alpha = 0.78$; and Productivity of Librarians $\alpha = 0.94$. With these results, the instrument was used for the study as the alpha reliability coefficient results for all the variables are more than 0.5 level of significant.

Research Procedure and Method of Data Collection

The corrected copies of the questionnaire were administered to professional librarians in all the fifty four (54) university libraries slated for the study. 923 copies of the corrected questionnaire were administered to librarians in all the 54 public university libraries slated for the study; out of which, a total number of 620 copies were retrieved. This gives 67.2% return rate of the administered research instrument for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected for this study was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), 22.0 latest versions. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics, especially for research questions 1-3, hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis.

Data Analysis, Results and Discussion of Findings

Presentation of Demographic Information of Respondents

Table 4.1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

S/N	DEMOGRAPHIC STATEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	Gender		
	Male	353	56.9
	Female	267	43.1
	Total	620	100.0
2.	Marital status		
	Single	114	18.4
	Married	455	73.4
	Divorced	33	5.3
	Widowed	18	2.9
	Total	620	100.0
3.	Age of respondents		
	Below 30	105	16.9
	31-40	186	30.0
	41-50	206	33.2
	51-60	116	18.7
	Above 60	7	1.1
	Total	620	100.0
4.	Educational qualification		
	BSc/BA	92	14.9
	BLIS	128	20.6
	MSc/MA	49	7.9

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, Rosaline Oluremi Opeke -
 THE CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, JOB SATISFACTION AND PRODUCTIVITY
 OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

	MLIS	312	50.3
	PhD	39	6.3
	Total	620	100.0
5.	Designation		
	Assistant Librarian	170	27.4
	Librarian II	133	21.5
	Librarian I	133	21.5
	Senior Librarian	81	13.1
	Principal Librarian	64	10.3
	Deputy University Librarian	27	4.4
	University Librarian	12	1.9
	Total	620	100.0
6.	Length of service		
	Below 6 years	213	34.4
	6-10 years	156	25.2
	11-15 years	108	17.4
	16-20years	52	8.4
	21-25 years	23	3.7
	26-30 years	54	8.7
	Above 30 years	14	2.3
	Total	620	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2016

From Table 2, it reveals that (56.9%) of the respondents were male. This implied that there were slightly more men in the librarianship profession than women in Nigeria. It was also revealed that majority of the respondents were married (73.4%). This implies that they would display maturity while discharging their duties to the library users in their various universities. It was revealed that there were more librarians in the age bracket of 41-50 years than any other age group closely followed by those in the age bracket 31-40. This simply meant a larger percentage of the respondents were relatively young and active.

Pertaining to the educational qualifications of the respondents, 50.3% were holders of Master's Degree in Library Science (MLIS) and others 20.6% were holders of Bachelor Degree in Library Science. This means that at least 71% of respondents were professionally qualified librarians. If it is assumed that the 6% who had Ph.D degrees got them from the field of librarianship, then this figure will increase to 77%. This shows that about a quarter (23%) of people working in Nigerian university libraries today hold degrees outside librarianship. This is understandable considering the role that information technology is playing in today's information provision services.

Data Analysis and Presentation Based on Research Questions

Research Question 1: *What is the degree of job satisfaction of librarians in public University Libraries in Nigeria?*

Table 3: Level of productivity of the respondents

S/N	STATEMENT	VH (%)	H (%)	M (%)	L (%)	Mean	SD	AM
a.	Students' academic success							
i.	Library collection enhances academic success of students in the university	411 (66.3)	181 (29.2)	26 (4.2)	2 (0.3)	3.64	0.540	3.56
ii.	Library provides conducive learning environment that encourages academic success	376 (60.6)	211 (34)	29 (4.7)	4 (0.8)	3.61	0.584	
iii.	With current and relevant library collections, students will excel in their academic programmes	323 (52.1)	260 (41.9)	32 (5.2)	5 (0.8)	3.55	0.617	
iv.	My job performance often lead to students' success in their examinations	356 (57.4)	221 (35.6)	38 (6.1)	5 (0.8)	3.45	0.633	
b.	Accreditation of more courses							
i.	My job performance contribute greatly to the accreditation exercises of the university	394 (63.5)	194 (31.3)	28 (4.5)	4 (0.6)	3.58	0.611	3.55
ii.	I actively involved in the accreditation exercises	390 (62.9)	203 (32.7)	22 (3.5)	5 (0.8)	3.58	0.603	
iii.	Relevant and current library collections help the university authority to have more courses accredited	385 (62.1)	189 (30.5)	40 (6.5)	6 (1)	3.54	0.661	
iv.	It encourages growth and development of the university	367 (59.2)	224 (36.1)	22 (3.5)	7 (1.1)	3.53	0.623	
v.	It enriches the university curricula and programmes.	356 (57.4)	221 (35.6)	38 (6.1)	5 (0.8)	3.50	0.649	
c.	Innovative research work							
i.	It provides resources for innovative research work.	362 (58.4)	226 (36.5)	27 (4.4)	5 (0.8)	3.52	0.621	3.51
ii.	My job output greatly contribute to the innovative research efforts of the university community	346 (55.8)	252 (40.6)	18 (2.9)	4 (0.6)	3.52	0.589	
iii.	It promotes the image of the university.	351 (56.6)	241 (38.9)	24 (3.9)	4 (0.6)	3.51	0.605	
iv.	My job performance contributes to	369	205	35	11	3.50	0.686	

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, Rosaline Oluremi Opeke -
 THE CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, JOB SATISFACTION AND PRODUCTIVITY
 OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

	innovative research work in the university.	(59.5)	(33.1)	(5.6)	(1.8)			
d.	Increase number of paper publication							
i.	Library collection boosts regular paper publications of faculty members.	436 (70.3)	156 (25.2)	25 (4)	3 (0.5)	3.61	0.550	3.39
ii.	It provides resources for regular paper publications	330 (53.2%)	256 (41.3)	30 (4.8)	4 (0.6)	3.47	0.621	
iii.	My regular paper publications assures me of promotion as at when due	331 (53.4)	248 (40)	31 (5)	10 (1.6)	3.45	0.667	
iv.	Three of my publications are in international journals	335 (54)	176 (28.4)	70 (11.3)	39 (6.3)	3.30	0.903	
v.	It enhances my regular paper publications.	395 (63.7)	180 (29)	36 (5.8)	9 (1.5)	3.26	0.989	
vi.	I have produced at least five papers in the past two years	305 (49.2)	202 (32.6)	82 (13.2)	31 (5)	3.26	0.871	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Key: VH = Very High, H = High, M = Medium, L = Low, SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean

It can be seen from Table 3 that librarians in Nigerian Universities considered their level of productivity to be very high judging by the average mean score of 3.39 on the scale of 4. They considered their contribution to the academic success of students as well as the universities' success in getting more courses accredited as the greatest measures of their productivity in the university system. Each had an average mean scores of 3.56 and 3.55 respectively. Specifically, having the relevant library collections (mean = 3.64) and conducive reading and learning environment contribute to students' academic success while active involvement in accreditation activities (mean = 3.58) plus having the right collection (mean = 3.58) contributed to the increase in the number of courses accredited, among others.

Research Question 2: *What is the level of productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?*

Table 4: Level of productivity of the respondents

S/N	STATEMENT	VH (%)	H (%)	M (%)	L (%)	Mean	SD	AM
a.	Students' academic success							
i.	Library collection enhances academic success of students in the university	411 (66.3)	181 (29.2)	26 (4.2)	2 (0.3)	3.64	0.540	

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, Rosaline Oluremi Opeke -
 THE CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, JOB SATISFACTION AND PRODUCTIVITY
 OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

ii.	Library provides conducive learning environment that encourages academic success	376 (60.6)	211 (34)	29 (4.7)	4 (0.8)	3.61	0.584	3.56
iii.	With current and relevant library collections, students will excel in their academic programmes	323 (52.1)	260 (41.9)	32 (5.2)	5 (0.8)	3.55	0.617	
iv.	My job performance often lead to students' success in their examinations	356 (57.4)	221 (35.6)	38 (6.1)	5 (0.8)	3.45	0.633	
b.	Accreditation of more courses							
i.	My job performance contribute greatly to the accreditation exercises of the university	394 (63.5)	194 (31.3)	28 (4.5)	4 (0.6)	3.58	0.611	3.55
ii.	I actively involved in the accreditation exercises	390 (62.9)	203 (32.7)	22 (3.5)	5 (0.8)	3.58	0.603	
iii.	Relevant and current library collections help the university authority to have more courses accredited	385 (62.1)	189 (30.5)	40 (6.5)	6 (1)	3.54	0.661	
iv.	It encourages growth and development of the university	367 (59.2)	224 (36.1)	22 (3.5)	7 (1.1)	3.53	0.623	
v.	It enriches the university curricula and programmes.	356 (57.4)	221 (35.6)	38 (6.1)	5 (0.8)	3.50	0.649	
c.	Innovative research work							
i.	It provides resources for innovative research work.	362 (58.4)	226 (36.5)	27 (4.4)	5 (0.8)	3.52	0.621	3.51
ii.	My job output greatly contribute to the innovative research efforts of the university community	346 (55.8)	252 (40.6)	18 (2.9)	4 (0.6)	3.52	0.589	
iii.	It promotes the image of the university.	351 (56.6)	241 (38.9)	24 (3.9)	4 (0.6)	3.51	0.605	
iv.	My job performance contribute to innovative research work in the university.	369 (59.5)	205 (33.1)	35 (5.6)	11 (1.8)	3.50	0.686	
d.	Increase number of paper publication							
i.	Library collection boosts regular paper publications of faculty members.	436 (70.3)	156 (25.2)	25 (4)	3 (0.5)	3.61	0.550	3.39
ii.	It provides resources for regular paper publications	330 (53.2%)	256 (41.3)	30 (4.8)	4 (0.6)	3.47	0.621	
iii.	My regular paper publications assures me of promotion as at when due	331 (53.4)	248 (40)	31 (5)	10 (1.6)	3.45	0.667	

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, Rosaline Oluremi Opeke -
 THE CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, JOB SATISFACTION AND PRODUCTIVITY
 OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

iv.	Three of my publications are in international journals	335 (54)	176 (28.4)	70 (11.3)	39 (6.3)	3.30	0.903
v.	It enhances my regular paper publications.	395 (63.7)	180 (29)	36 (5.8)	9 (1.5)	3.26	0.989
vi.	I have produced at least five papers in the past two years	305 (49.2)	202 (32.6)	82 (13.2)	31 (5)	3.26	0.871

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Key: VH = Very High, H = High, M = Medium, L = Low, SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean

It can be seen from Table 4 that librarians in Nigerian Universities considered their level of productivity to be very high judging by the average mean score of 3.39 on the scale of 4. They considered their contribution to the academic success of students as well as the universities' success in getting more courses accredited as the greatest measures of their productivity in the university system. Each had an average mean scores of 3.56 and 3.55 respectively. Specifically, having the relevant library collections (mean = 3.64) and conducive reading and learning environment contribute to students' academic success while active involvement in accreditation activities (mean = 3.58) plus having the right collection (mean = 3.58) contributed to the increase in the number of courses accredited, among others.

Research Question 3: *What is the level of emotional intelligence of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria?*

Table 5: Level of emotional intelligence and productivity of the respondents

S/N	STATEMENT	VGE (%)	GE (%)	ME (%)	NE (%)	MEAN	SD	AM
a.	Relationship management							
i.	Positive impact on others	367 (59.2)	205 (33.1)	36 (5.8)	12 (1.9)	3.50	0.695	3.44
ii.	Collaboration and cooperation	339 (54.7)	258 (41.6)	11 (1.8)	12 (1.9)	3.49	0.634	
iii.	Conflict management	348 (56.1)	220 (35.5)	51 (8.2)	1 (0.2)	3.48	0.651	
iv.	Communication	343 (55.3)	243 (39.2)	25 (4)	9 (1.5)	3.48	0.647	
v.	Building bonds	329 (53.1)	253 (40.8)	34 (5.5)	4 (0.6)	3.46	0.631	
vi.	Influence i.e. Influencing others	337 (54.4)	226 (36.5)	40 (6.5)	17 (2.7)	3.42	0.734	
vii.	Developing others	331 (53.4)	216 (34.8)	61 (9.8)	12 (1.9)	3.40	0.744	

Japheth Abdulazeez Yaya, Rosaline Oluremi Opeke -
 THE CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, JOB SATISFACTION AND PRODUCTIVITY
 OF LIBRARIANS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

vii.	Change catalyst	312 (50.3)	245 (39.5)	52 (8.4)	11 (1.8)	3.38	0.715	
ix.	Teamwork	298 (48.1)	245 (39.5)	71 (11.5)	6 (1)	3.35	0.717	
b.	Self-awareness							
i.	Self-confidence/esteem	341 (55)	242 (39)	25 (4)	12 (1.9)	3.47	0.668	3.42
ii.	Accurate self-assessment/evaluation	356 (57.4)	195 (31.5)	56 (9)	13 (2.1)	3.44	0.744	
iii.	Emotional self-awareness	324 (52.3)	210 (33.9)	65 (10.5)	21 (3.4)	3.35	0.801	
c.	Self-management							
i.	Growth orientation	328 (52.9)	259 (41.8)	28 (4.5)	5 (0.8)	3.47	0.623	3.42
ii.	Innovation	349 (56.8)	221 (35.6)	32 (5.2)	18 (2.9)	3.45	0.725	
iii.	Trustworthiness	343 (55.3)	231 (37.3)	26 (4.2)	20 (3.2)	3.45	0.725	
iv.	Optimism/positivism	340 (54.8)	219 (35.3)	56 (9)	5 (0.8)	3.44	0.690	
v.	Initiative	335 (54)	224 (36.1)	52 (8.4)	9 (1.5)	3.43	0.707	
vi.	Conscientiousness	325 (52.4)	226 (36.5)	55 (8.9)	14 (2.3)	3.39	0.743	
vii.	Self-control	332 (53.5)	213 (34.4)	60 (9.7)	15 (2.4)	3.39	0.740	
viii.	Adaptability	308 (49.7)	262 (42.3)	35 (5.6)	15 (2.4)	3.39	0.705	
ix.	Achievement drive	302 (48.7)	247 (39.8)	59 (9.5)	12 (1.9)	3.35	0.732	
d.	Social-awareness							
v.	Leadership	300 (48.4)	272 (43.9)	46 (7.4)	2 (0.3)	3.40	0.640	3.32
vi.	Empathy	276 (44.5)	293 (47.3)	45 (7.3)	6 (1)	3.35	0.658	
vii.	Organizational commitment	278 (44.8)	276 (44.5)	60 (9.7)	6 (1)	3.33	0.689	
viii.	Achievement/service orientation	278 (44.8)	269 (43.4)	66 (10.6)	7 (1.1)	3.32	0.706	
ix.	Organizational awareness	247 (39.8)	281 (45.3)	66 (10.6)	26 (4.2)	3.21	0.794	

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Key: VGE = Very Great Extent; GE = Great Extent; ME = Moderate Extent; NE = No Extent;

SD = Standard Deviation; AM = Average Mean

Table 5 shows that librarians in Nigerian Universities considered their level of emotional intelligence to be very high judging by the average mean score of 3.32 on the scale of 4. They considered their relational management of the library users as well as their self-awareness ability as the greatest measures of their emotional intelligence in the university system. Each had an average mean scores of 3.44 and 3.42 respectively. Specifically, having ability to make positive impact on others especially university students (mean = 3.50) followed by their collaboration and cooperation (mean = 3.49) with others especially with similar academic libraries in meeting the information needs of library users while self-confidence/esteem (mean = 3.47) plus having the accurate self-assessment or evaluation (mean = 3.44) contributed to increase in their productivity in the university library, among others.

Hypotheses Testing and Interpretation

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction in public university libraries in Nigeria.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis between Emotional Intelligence and Job Satisfaction in Public University Libraries in Nigeria

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	N	R	P	Remark
Emotional Intelligence	3.31	0.82	620	0.034	0.000	Sig.
Job Satisfaction	3.47	0.62				

Significant at 0.05 level

The mean score of the emotional intelligence of librarians in Nigerian university libraries was 3.31, SD = 0.82 while that of job satisfaction was 3.47, SD = 0.62. The correlation coefficient obtained was 0.034 with p-value < 0.05. The result showed positive correlation between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of librarians. There was a positive significant relationship between the variables as indicated in the above table as (r = 0.034, N = 620, P < 0.05). Null hypothesis four is rejected. This indicates that there is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

Table 4.12: Correlation Analysis between Emotional Intelligence and Productivity of Librarians in Public University Libraries in Nigeria

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	N	R	P	Remark
Emotional Intelligence	3.21	0.79	620	0.032	0.000	Sig.
Productivity	3.55	0.67				

Significant at 0.05 level

The mean score of the emotional intelligence of librarians in Nigerian university libraries was 3.21, SD = 0.79 while that of productivity was 3.55, SD = 0.67. The correlation coefficient obtained was 0.032 with p-value < 0.05. The result showed positive correlation between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians. There was a positive significant relationship between the variables as indicated in the above table as (r = 0.032, N = 620, P < 0.05). Null hypothesis five is rejected. This indicates that there is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This section discussed the major findings of this study in relation to past studies. The discussion followed the research questions on which sources of relationships between emotional intelligence, job satisfaction and productivity of librarians were established through past empirical studies. The findings of the study are discussed as follows:

Research question one showed that librarians considered their being recognised by the authorities as well as good leadership styles that were practised as the greatest measures of their job satisfaction in the university system. The results were supported by the submissions of Singh and Jain (2013); Chuks-Ibe and Ozioko, 2014; Noor et al, 2015 who submitted that job satisfaction of an employee in the organization was the collection of positive and/or negative feelings that an individual holds toward his or her job. They reported that achievement depends on employee satisfaction and in turn contribute to organizational success and growth. They concluded in their studies that job satisfaction boosts productivity of employees in the organization.

The findings were also supported by Russell (2008) as well as [Massachusetts Institute of Technology](#) (2014) who submitted in their findings that employee recognition was a motivational element that could be applied in the managerial level to motivate the employees for better job performance and being more innovative. They further stressed that recognition was a positive feedback that enabled employees to know that they were valued and appreciated by their employers and co-workers.

Research question two showed that librarians' contribution to the academic success of students as well as the universities' success in getting more courses accredited as the greatest measures of their productivity in the university system. The findings implied that library was fundamental to research productivity and that it supported the curricula of the universities. These were consistent with the research conducted by Okonedo et al (2015) in which the research productivity of various academic staff in the university was found relatively high in order to assure their chances of being promoted to the next position. It was revealed in the study that librarians' job performance often lead to students' academic success in their examinations; library provided students with current and relevant library collections and these help students to excel in their various academic programmes. Also, library equally provided conducive and quiet learning environment that encouraged users' personal reading and students' academic success as its collections enhanced academic success of students in the university.

Research question three showed that librarians considered their relational management of the library users as well as their self-awareness ability as the greatest measures of their emotional intelligence in the university system. Specifically, having ability to make positive impact on others especially university students (mean = 3.50) followed by their collaboration and cooperation (mean = 3.49) with others especially with similar academic libraries in meeting the information needs of library users.

It was revealed by the respondents that librarians were to make positive impact on other people especially library users, in which students constituted highest number in the university system. This result agreed with the position of Ziv (2014), who noted that, an individual who has a strong effect on the behaviour of another person or group of people in the organization or in the entire human society. He believed that these types of people were able to help other people in the organization to see the big picture and influenced them in seeking out desired positive outcomes while adhering to ethical values and principles.

Furthermore, the findings and analysis presented in Table 6, the null hypothesis four was rejected. This indicates a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of librarians in the public university libraries in Nigeria ($r = 0.034$, $P < 0.05$). The finding supported the previous studies of Guleryüz et al (2008), Mousavi et al (2012), Ogungbeni et al (2013) and Orhan and Dincer (2014) who affirmed the significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence of librarians and their job satisfaction. This implied that there was direct relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of librarians in the university library.

Also, from the findings and analysis presented in Table 4.12, the null hypothesis five was rejected. This indicates that there was a significant relationship between

emotional intelligence and productivity of librarians in the public university libraries in Nigeria ($r = 0.032$, $P < 0.05$). The finding corresponds with previous studies conducted by some scholars; few of these studies were here presented: Salovey and Mayer (1990), Goleman (2005), Sahdat et al (2011), Zaki et al (2012), Javidparvar et al (2013), Kalitani (2013), Orluwene and Wachukwu (2014) and Zobisch (2014) to establish the relationship between emotional intelligence and productivity of employees in the organization. This showed that a worker who had a good knowledge of his/her emotion would be more productive than other workers who have no such knowledge.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary of Findings

The major findings of the study were as follows:

1. Librarians in Nigerian Universities saw their level of job satisfaction as very high judging by the average mean score of 3.13 on a scale of 4. They attributed this to being recognised by the authorities as well as good leadership styles that were practised as the greatest measures of their job satisfaction in the university system.
2. Librarians' level of productivity was also high judging by the average mean score of 3.39 on the scale of 4. They considered their contribution to students' academic success and the universities' success in getting more courses accredited as major measures of their level of productivity.
3. Librarians' level of emotional intelligence was very high judging by the average mean score of 3.32 on the scale of 4. They attributed this to their relational management of the library users as well as their self-awareness ability as major measures of their emotional intelligence in the university system.

Conclusion

The study had succeeded in disabusing the earlier submission of low level job satisfaction and productivity of library personnel judging from its findings. It was directed towards librarians' welfare and personal issues such as emotional intelligence on one side with job satisfaction and productivity on the other side. The study established that emotional intelligence was positively correlated with job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in the Nigerian public university libraries.

Besides, the study confirmed the assertion that emotional intelligence enhances job satisfaction and productivity of workers in any organization especially in the public

university libraries as an emotionally stabled librarian is a happy, satisfied and productive librarian. Therefore, in the public university institutions, the welfare of librarians should be taken seriously. Hence, the findings and recommendations that emanated from this study would be relevant to our local needs in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and challenges that were revealed in this study, the following recommendations are hereby proffered as the way forward:

1. Lower level of career advancement opportunities when compared with employee recognition job satisfaction factor, suggests that librarians may lack adequate sponsorship to attend international conferences. The researchers recommend that the university authorities should allocate reasonable fund in her annual budget mainly for sponsoring librarians to attend both local and international conferences, seminars, and workshops in order to equip them to effectively discharge their professional duties.
2. The study revealed decrease in paper publications among librarians and other faculty members in the last two years. This was attributed to general observation that most Nigerian public university libraries were stocked with irrelevant, old and obsolete resources that could not be used for any meaningful research work. It is therefore imperative for the university libraries in Nigeria to be stocked with current and relevant educational resources that would boost high class research works.
3. Lower level of extrinsic motivation when compared with intrinsic motivation, suggests that librarians may lack some physiological needs. This was attributed to lack of conducive work environment in most Nigerian public university libraries. The university authorities should provide librarians with a befitting and conducive work environment; their offices should be well furnished with modern day equipment and working tools that would facilitate information service delivery to various information seekers.
4. Lower level of social awareness emotional intelligence component when compared with that of relationship management. This suggested that librarians were lacking organization awareness competency. Librarians were expected to have full knowledge of the entire organization they were expected to serve. They were to carry out users' analysis in order to have full knowledge of their information needs. This could be done through questionnaire, internal memo to heads of department and experts on each subject field soliciting for their input in

the selection process, publishers' catalogues as well as relevant book vendor list could be sent to each subject experts to select appropriate texts, amongst other methods.

5. The study revealed low level career development in comparison with manpower training programme in most Nigerian public university libraries. This was attributed to inadequate career development programmes in most public university libraries. Every library should put in place a well-designed career development programme for its personnel especially librarians. Librarianship subject experts and other professionals in psychology, ICT and other relevant fields should be engaged to conduct periodic in-house training/career development programmes for the librarians in order to boost their productivity.
6. The study equally revealed that job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in most Nigerian public university libraries were been challenged by non-payment of similar allowances payable to other academic staff as well as inadequate employee recognition and marginalization of librarians by the university authorities. The university authorities should mete out equal treatment to every academic staff and none should be marginalized nor given higher priority over the others. In other words, no academic staff should be treated as a core staff or regarded as a very important personality (VIP) over the others. Hence, they should be paid equal salaries and allowances in line with the government approved salary structures. Also, librarians should be given adequate recognition as custodians and managers of information resources needed in supporting the curricula of each academic programme in the university system.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The present study focused on the emotional intelligence as correlates of job satisfaction and productivity of librarians in public University libraries in Nigeria. The study surveyed all the public universities in North-Central, North-West, South-East and South-West geopolitical zones in Nigeria. Therefore, the following areas of study are suggested for further research:

1. An investigation on how librarians in the Public Universities in North-East and South-South geopolitical zones of Nigeria perceive the factors identified in this study in relationship to their job satisfaction and productivity.
2. A study on how librarians in the Private Universities in Nigeria perceive the factors identified in this study in relationship to their job satisfaction and productivity.

3. A study on how librarians in other Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria perceive the factors identified in this study in relationship to their job satisfaction and productivity.
4. A study on how the perceptions of librarians in the Public Universities in Nigeria compare with those of the librarians in Private Universities.
5. This study limits itself to only twenty six emotional intelligence competencies, it is important to further investigate into various other emotional intelligence competencies that would boost the productivity of workers in the university system or in similar institutions of higher learning.

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